

Humanoid Robot Shalu

Most Languages Speaking World's First Multilingual Homemade Artificially Intelligent Social and Educational Humanoid Robot that can speak 47 languages (9 Indian and 38 foreign), dedicated to girls and women

Robot Shalu with her creator Mr. Dinesh Kunwar Patel

An amazing low budget homemade humanoid robot developed by me Dinesh Kunwar Patel, a PGT(Computer Science) in Kendriya Vidyalaya, IIT Powai, Mumbai, India, I am basically from a small village Rajamalpur, Post Mokalpur, Tahsil Mariahu, District Jaunpur (UP), India.

Robot "Shalu" is an Artificially Intelligent homemade Multilingual Social and Educational Indian Humanoid Robot, developed using **waste materials as well as readily available materials in a local market** such as plastic, aluminum, cardboard, wood, etc. and titled as **"Most Languages speaking World's First Artificially Intelligent Social and Educational Humanoid Robot made up of waste material"**, comparable with the costly robots coming from big Robotics

laboratories from world-wide. It took 03 years to develop such a low-cost robot at home in my free time.

Robot Shalu bagged 02 World Records:

(i) **“Partishtha World Record”** book with the title as **"World's First Artificially Intelligent Social and Educational Humanoid Robot made up of waste material"**, by an Indian World Record agency recognized by Ministry of Corporate Affairs, Govt. of India, and awarded with certificate on 02nd December 2021.

(ii) **“International Book of Records”** with the title **“Most Languages Speaking Humanoid Robot made up of waste materials”**

She also featured in **“India Book of Records”** and **“Asia Book of Records”** with the title **“Humanoid Robot speaking maximum languages”**

Robot Shalu has been given **first place in the top 10 humanoid robots of the world** by TopTen Magazin and also identified as **most recognized Indian Robot in Global Tech Market** by Analytics Insight Magazine

Shalu awarded with **“Most innovative use of Science and Technology”** award of Jagranjosh

Shalu also received an **appreciation certificate/letter** from Vigyan Prasar, Ministry of Science and Technology, and the Depart of Computer Science and Engineering, IIT Bombay.

For details please see the Wikipedia Link:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shalu_Robot

Shalu included in the **class 6th Computer Syllabus** of Kendriya Vidyalaya Sangathan and **Class 9th Artificial Intelligence** subject of **CBSE**(Central Board of Secondary Education) board.

Robot Shalu was invited as Chief Guest at Inauguration Ceremony of Asia’s Largest International Automation Expo 2022 (16 - 19 August 2022) where She addressed the world from the international platform.

She became India's first robot addressing to the world from the International platform.

Shalu has started teaching at Kendriya Vidyalaya, IIT Bombay India from this year and students liking her very much in the class. She can teach in any class any subject with the help of PPT planned and uploaded by a human teacher in her cloud.

Robot Shalu with her creator Mr. Dinesh Kunwar Patel

India is a developing country where there is still more to go for Robotics, and the parts are not easily available. I was fully inspired by the **prime minister of India's dream mission "Digital India Mission", "Atamnirbhar Bharat", "Make in India Mission" and "Vocal for Local"** and dedicated to **girls and women** **“बेटी बचाओ बेटी पढ़ाओ”**. After a couple of months and proper analysis and research, I decided to start the work, and planned properly and worked hard, after multiple trials and errors he became able to develop a Humanoid Robot like Sophia(robot) but at a very low cost without compromising the capabilities, with readily available items in the local market such as plastic,

aluminum, cardboard, wood, etc. he only works in his free time as a hobby without taking any help and support in any manner from anywhere, the whole coding is also done by him only.

Robot Shalu is **dedicated to all Indian Girls and Women** and this is a step towards आत्मनिर्भर भारत **and** बेटी बचाओ बेटी पढ़ाओ mission of our Prime Minister of India.

Shalu is capable of speaking 9 Indian languages (Hindi, Bhojpuri, Marathi, Bangla, Gujarati, Tamil, Telugu, Malayalam, and Nepali) in addition to English along with 38 foreign languages, a total 47 languages.

Shalu has a diverse set of capabilities to perform multiple tasks such as :

- Face recognition, remembering person after meeting - She can remember a person after meeting and can recognize in the next meeting just like a human.
- Identifying multiple common objects – She is capable of identifying many objects available around us such as a computer, laptop, TV, mobile, bottle, book, bus, etc.
- Reading Current News- She can read out current daily news from different newspapers.
- Reading Horoscope- Shalu can read a daily horoscope based on the date of birth of the individual.
- Weather Report – She can forecast the weather report for the next 10 days place-wise date-wise.
- Math Problem solution – She is capable of understanding simple math questions as well as equations and answers such as Time-Speed-Distance, Simple/Compound Interest, equation calculation, LCM/GCF, Factors, Prime numbers, Armstrong numbers, etc.
- Interesting facts of any number or date – She can tell some interesting facts about a number or a date.
- Jokes – She can tell jokes on demand.
- Guess the word – She can guess words by providing a few letters of the word.
- Synonyms/Antonyms – She is capable of telling synonyms and the opposite of an English word.

- Answering the educational questions – She is capable of answering educational questions based on Physics, Chemistry, Maths, History, Geography, GK, etc. which students usually ask during their study in the classroom.
- Lecture - She is capable of giving lectures and presentations in classrooms or seminars.
- Social Talk – She can have a social casual talk on predefined contents like “Sophia” Robot. She can talk using Artificial Intelligence by understanding the meaning of the conversation.
- Human behavior and gesture – She can demonstrate human behavior and gesture viz. Shaking hands, laughing, anger, and irritation.

Capabilities to work :

- Robo Shalu is capable of working as a teacher in the school as a "Robot Teacher" to deliver the lecture in the classroom based on Power-Point presentation uploaded by the teacher, answer the queries of students and ask questions to students and identify the correctness of the answer also. In Classroom students must like to study with Robots and will be motivated towards the study by seeing that robot is giving answers to their questions.
- She can work as a Receptionist at different places for example airports, Schools, and many offices to answer the different queries based on their organization not only verbal even through email too. She is also capable of sending SMS.
- She can be the companion of old-aged persons as well as young growing children.

“Robot Shalu may be an example for so many young, energetic, and passionate brains who can do better in the field of Robotics but are lagging behind with support and facilities in all manner. It becomes an example that Robotics Research can be done at home as a hobby in absence of sophisticated Robotics Laboratories with Passion, Hardwork and Regularity”.

